

Research Article

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A Machine Learning Approach to Predict Employee Churn

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Abstract

Organizations face significant challenges due to employee turnover, impacting competitiveness, customer satisfaction, and operational efficiency. This study explores the potential of machine learning methods in predicting and mitigating staff attrition, using a comprehensive dataset from Kaggle comprising 14,999 samples with various employee-related variables. The Gradient Boosting Classifier (GBC) was identified as the optimal model for predicting employee turnover, based on comprehensive exploratory data analysis, model training, and performance evaluation. In addition, the investigation reveals interesting trends and connections that underscore important variables that influence employee churn, including job satisfaction, workplace problems, and length of service. Furthermore, the significance of data pretreatment methods, such as label encoding and oversampling, in improving model performance and addressing class imbalance is discussed. This research aims to empower Human Resources (HR) professionals and organizational leaders with actionable insights and methodologies to implement targeted retention strategies and cultivate a more stable and productive workforce.

Keywords: Machine Learning, Predictive Modelling, Gradient Boosting Classifier, Employee Turnover, HR Analytics,

1. Introduction

The issue of employee turnover has gained significant attention in businesses due to its detrimental effects on various aspects, including productivity and workplace morale. Predicting employee churn enables organizations to identify at-risk employees and implement targeted, proactive retention measures before separations occur (Bayrak, A.T., Yüçetürk, G., Bahadır, M. B., Yalcinkaya, S. M., Demirag, M. & Sayan, I.U., 2022). Employee turnover remains a persistent challenge for HR functions and carries substantial financial costs: estimates from the Center for American Progress indicate that replacing a typical employee costs approximately 20% of annual salary, with markedly higher costs for executives and top earners (Simhoni, 2023). Accordingly, systematically monitoring indicators of job dissatisfaction and intent to quit is essential for timely, data-driven intervention. The high rate of staff turnover also raises the price of recruiting, firing, training, and advertising. The expense of replacing a departing employee is almost double their salary, and the detrimental effects are roughly the same across all industries. The employee turnover rate for HR service firms is notably high, ranging from 12 to 15%. The cost of an employee leaving a company is almost 1.5 times their yearly income, even at a lower churn rate of 5%. This is a very high churn rate (Saradhi, V. V., & Palshikar, G.K, 2011). The minority (leaver) class is relatively small, which motivates imbalance-aware evaluation.

This study presents a comprehensive analysis of machine learning techniques aimed at predicting employee churn. Leveraging a rich dataset encompassing diverse employee attributes, such as satisfaction levels (Guggenberger, P.,

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Maor, D., Park, M., & Simon, P., 2023), performance evaluations, tenure, and departmental affiliations, the study embarked on a rigorous exploration to uncover key determinants influencing employee departure decisions. Several statistical issues have seen the use of classification techniques. It is important to appropriately comprehend the study of these strategies and their relevance while assessing various learning algorithms (Ilter, D., Kocadagli, O. & Ravishanker, N, 2019).

Literature extensively explores various categorization techniques, with a predominant emphasis on Binary Classification Models. However, the traditional methods are criticized due to various prerequisites and linear approximations in high-dimensional and excessive nonlinear cases. For this reason, artificial intelligence techniques are mostly preferred to handle credit scoring problems accurately by Python.

A company that has a high turnover suffers from several negative repercussions. Experts in a particular business domain or specialized skill sets are hard to replace. It has an impact on current employees' productivity and ongoing work.

In Engin and Fakhouri's study, a detailed analysis using Random Forest (RF), GBC, Extreme Gradient Boosting (EGB), Light Gradient Boosting Machine (LGBM), Decision Tree Classifier (DTC), Extra Trees Classifier (ETC) and Naive Bayes (NB) algorithms evaluate the performance of different models built to compare businesses quarters in the loan classification process. It highlights the role of cash flow data in the process (Engin, E., & Fakhouri I. D., 2024).

Hiring and training new hires as a replacement comes with their own set of expenses. Additionally, there will be learning curves for new hires before they reach the same levels of business or technical proficiency as a seasoned internal employee (Punnoose, R., & Ajit, P., 2016).

Employers' efforts to retain current employees relate directly to job satisfaction. Keeping current employees on board is better than hiring new ones. Maintaining wholesome employees has always been crucial. Employers and workers are unique. They are not the ones without good prospects by any means. The reason for maintaining staff is that a firm needs healthy, devoted, well-trained, and diligent workers to operate it (Chakraborty, R., Mridha, K., Shaw, R. N., & Ghosh A., 2021).

Additional studies on the use of data mining in customer interactions may be found in (Ngai, E.W.T., Xiu, L. & Chau, D.C.K., 2009). Data mining is so frequently utilized in a range of application areas pertaining to HR. Various statistical techniques are employed in (Sikaroudi, A.E., & Rouzbehghousi, E., 2015) to predict employee turnover based on personal information and the worker's past. Machine learning has several applications, which include predicting and categorization of various HR data characteristics and traits. When factors like tardiness, absenteeism, and employee indifference are taken into consideration for predicting employee performance, (Ngai, E.W.T., Xiu, L. & Chau, D.C.K., 2009) achieves the early projection of employee turnover.

Employee turnover imposes substantial operational and financial costs, motivating accurate prediction of voluntary exits so that organizations can target retention actions proactively. While numerous machine learning approaches have been explored for churn-type problems, evidence on employee churn remains fragmented, and many studies conflate methodological reporting with results, limiting reproducibility and practical uptake.

The initial exploratory data analysis (EDA) phase illuminated significant patterns, highlighting the nuanced interplay between factors, including satisfaction levels, occurrences of work-related accidents, promotions, and tenure within the organization. Building upon these insights, a meticulously curated preprocessing and data modeling framework was developed to apply machine learning algorithms for churn prediction. A variety of models were examined in the study, including the NB, K-Nearest Neighbors (KNN), Support Vector Machine (SVM), GBC, and Logistic Regression (LR). Each model was assessed using performance metrics, including accuracy, precision, recall, and area under the receiver operating characteristic curve (AUC-ROC).

Notably, the findings underscored the superior predictive capabilities of the GBC, evidenced by its exceptional accuracy, precision, and recall scores. This highlights the efficacy of advanced machine learning methodologies in preemptively identifying potential instances of employee churn. Such insights hold immense promises for organizations seeking to implement targeted retention strategies and cultivate a conducive work environment conducive to long-term employee engagement and productivity.

Existing work typically reports headline accuracy/AUC without transparent preprocessing pipelines for mixed data (categorical, ordinal, continuous), principled treatment of class imbalance, and critical interpretation of model trade-offs for decision support (e.g., precision vs. recall under limited retention budgets).

This research analyzes an anonymized company-level HR dataset with demographic, role, workload, performance, and satisfaction variables, where the target is a binary indicator of employee exit. The class distribution is imbalanced (minority = leavers). The intricacies of the methodology are explored, comprehensive model comparisons are conducted, and a detailed analysis of the GBC is provided. By furnishing actionable insights tailored for human resources professionals and organizational leaders, the study aims to facilitate effective mitigation of employee churn and foster a more stable and productive workforce.

This study provides a transparent, reproducible pipeline for employee churn prediction (encoding, scaling, leakage-free resampling, and model evaluation), compares widely-used algorithms under a consistent protocol, and reports metrics suited to imbalance (AUC-ROC, accuracy, precision, recall), with uncertainty estimates, and translates model outputs into tuning parameters to support retention decisions.

2. Motivation and Overview

Figure 1 presents the experimental workflow—implemented in Python (pandas, scikit-learn)—beginning with data ingestion and preprocessing, followed by Synthetic Minority Over-Sampling Technique (SMOTE) within training folds, model training and hyperparameter tuning via stratified cross-validation, and final hold-out evaluation. (HR_Dataset, 2023) to facilitate data handling and analysis. The process continues with loading the HR dataset, followed by applying EDA techniques to gain insights. This includes computing descriptive statistics, detecting missing values, and visualizing data distributions through distribution plots. Subsequently, duplicate rows are identified and removed to enhance data accuracy.

Categorical variables are encoded using label encoding for ordinal variables and one-hot encoding for nominal variables, followed by feature scaling using StandardScaler. Class imbalance within the dataset is addressed through oversampling using the SMOTE (Chawla, 2002) method. Class imbalance was addressed with SMOTE applied only to training folds to prevent leakage; Adaptive Synthetic Sampling Approach for Imbalanced Learning (ADASYN) was not used to keep sampling constant across folds. However, the resulting 70% - 30% train-test split serves as the basis for future model training and assessment operations.

Furthermore, the dataset is divided into training and testing subsets, and the experimental procedures conclude with the identification of key factors influencing employee turnover. These include promotions, tenure, number of projects, and salary levels, providing real-world scenarios for informing decision-making in HR management and organizational strategy.

Figure 1. The flowchart of the proposed procedure.

In the study, the main aim is to predict the employees' churn status. To predict the churn class of employees, commonly used classification methods are built as a baseline. GBC (Friedman, J. H., 2001), LR (Cox, 1958), SVM (Cortes, C., & Vapnik, V., 1995), KNN (Cover, T., & Hart, P., 1967), and NB (Domingos, P., & Pazzani, M., 1997; Rish, I., 2001) were evaluated under a common protocol and showed AUC-ROC, accuracy, precision, and recall.

The GBC was selected as the primary model owing to its sequential ensemble methodology. Unlike approaches that aim to construct a single strong classifier, boosting techniques and ensemble methods focus on training multiple weak classifiers and systematically combining their outputs to achieve superior predictive performance. GBC iteratively fits shallow trees to residuals, improving fit on hard cases.

LR, a cornerstone of statistical modelling for binary classification tasks, provided real-world scenarios into event likelihood based on input features. Its performance metrics elucidated its predictive capabilities, informing its suitability for churn prediction tasks.

Integration of the SVM model yielded promising results, leveraging its capacity to delineate classes effectively within high-dimensional feature spaces. The model's accuracy, precision, and recall metrics underscored its robust predictive performance within the dataset. Similarly, the KNN classifier demonstrated strong predictive capabilities, with simplicity and effectiveness in capturing patterns within the data. Its reliable performance metrics positioned KNN as a robust tool for predictive modelling in the study. Furthermore, NB, despite its simplistic assumptions, exhibited utility in churn prediction tasks. Its performance metrics, particularly its high recall rate, highlighted its effectiveness in identifying instances of churn within the dataset (Ferreira, A.J., & Figueiredo, M.A.T., 2012).

The comprehensive evaluation of these machine learning models, as provided in Table 1, including GBC, LR, SVM, KNN, and NB, provided real-world scenarios into their respective strengths and limitations for churn prediction. These findings offer significant implications for their application in real-world scenarios, contributing to the advancement of predictive modelling methodologies in the context of employee churn/turnover analysis.

Table 1. Machine learning classification algorithms: A comparison table with formulas.

Algorithm	Formulas
GBC	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> * Loss Function (Log Loss): $L(y, F(x)) = -\sum[y * \log(p) + (1-y) * \log(1-p)]$ * Update Predictions: $F(x) = F(x) + \eta * h(x)$, ($h(x)$ is the prediction from a new tree, η is the learning rate)
LR	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> * Logistic Function (Sigmoid): $p(y=1) = 1 / (1 + e^{-(b_0 + b_1x_1 + \dots + b_nx_n)})$ * Log-Likelihood (Loss Function): $L(y, p) = -\sum[y * \log(p) + (1-y) * \log(1-p)]$
SVM	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> * Decision Function: $f(x) = b + w_1x_1 + \dots + w_nx_n$ * Hinge Loss: $L(y, f(x)) = \max(0, 1 - y * f(x))$
KNN	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> * Distance Measure (Euclidean Distance): $d(x, x_i) = \sqrt{(\sum(x_j - x_{ij})^2)}$ * Majority Vote: Assign the class label that appears most often among the k nearest neighbors.
NB	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> * Bayes' Theorem: $P(y x) = (P(y) \prod_{i=1}^n P(x_i y)) / P(x)$ * Naive Assumption: $P(x_i y)$ are assumed independent for each feature x_i

As illustrated in Table 1, introduce a novel approach leveraging mathematical notation to enhance the clarity of the methodology in the domain of classification tasks. Specifically, denote Σ as the symbol for summation, facilitating concise representation of cumulative operations. The term $d(x, x_i)$ is utilized to denote the distance between a data point x and its respective neighbor x_i , aiding in the elucidation of proximity-based computations. The study employee $p(y|x)$ to signify the conditional probability of class y given features x , and $p(y|x)$ to denote the likelihood of observing features x giving class y , enabling transparent articulation of probabilistic reasoning. Moreover, to incorporate $p(y)$ to denote the prior probability of class y , providing insight into the preexisting distribution of classes within the dataset. The symbol $p(x)$ is utilized to represent total probability, often serving as a constant in classification tasks, streamlining the discussion of overall likelihood considerations. Additionally, to utilize b_0, b_1, \dots, b_n to denote the coefficients or weights learned by the model, facilitating clarity in expressing the learned parameters.

Furthermore, w_1, w_2, \dots, w_n are introduced as weights associated with individual features in SVM decision function, aiding in the comprehension of feature importance within the classification framework. Lastly, incorporate η as the symbol for the learning rate in gradient boosting algorithms, The loss function as shown in Equation (1) denoted as $L(y, F(x))$, measures the discrepancy between the true target values (y) and the predictions made by the model $F(x)$. In the context of binary classification, the commonly used loss function is the binary cross-entropy loss, which is expressed as:

$$\text{Loss Function: } L(y, F(x)) = -\sum [y \cdot \log(p) + (1 - y) \cdot \log(1 - p)]. \tag{1}$$

Here, p represents the predicted probability of the positive class. This loss function penalizes the model more heavily for making incorrect predictions, especially for high-confidence wrong predictions (i.e., large deviations between y and p). After obtaining the current predictions $F(x)$, the residuals (r) are calculated by subtracting the true target values (y) from the predictions. Mathematically, this step is represented in Equation (2) as:

$$\text{Calculate Residuals: } r = y - F(x). \tag{2}$$

The residuals represent the errors made by the current model. These errors are used to train the next weak learner (usually a decision tree) in the ensemble. Finally, the predictions $F(x)$ are updated by adding the predictions of a new tree, which is trained to predict the residuals (r). The learning rate or shrinkage parameter (η) controls the contribution of each new tree prediction to the overall ensemble. The updated predictions are calculated as:

$$\text{Update Predictions: } F(x) = F(x) + \eta \cdot \text{new tree prediction}. \tag{3}$$

By iteratively adding new weak learners and updating the predictions, the model gradually improves its ability to capture the underlying patterns in the data and minimize the loss function, enabling straightforward communication of optimization parameterization. By employing these standardized notations, the research aims to enhance the accessibility and comprehensibility of the proposed methodologies within the scientific community.

3. Methodology and Application

The analysis of visualization outcomes revealed several critical insights into employee behavior and organizational dynamics, as demonstrated in Table 2. Firstly, it was observed that most employees were engaged in projects.

Table 2. Key factors influencing employee turnover.

Factor	Observation	Potential Impact on Turnover
Project Range	Majority (3-5 projects)	May indicate a common workload, but a decline in retention after 3 years (potential burnout for 6+ projects)
Tenure (Years)	Decline (3-4 years)	Potential turning point in commitment
Tenure (Years)	Lower (5 years)	Lack of promotions might be a factor
Tenure (Years)	Higher (6+ years)	Increased organizational loyalty
Promotions	Not received by a significant portion	May contribute to dissatisfaction
Department	Sales (highest number)	Provides insight into organizational structure
Salary	Medium or low (prevalent)	Highlights the prevalent compensation structure

The range is from 3 to 5, suggesting a common workload distribution within the workforce. However, a notable decline in retention rates was observed between employees with 3 and 4 years of experience, indicating a potential turning point in employee commitment at the three-year mark. Furthermore, the analysis indicated that approximately 16% of the total workforce had left the company, highlighting a substantial turnover rate. Additionally, a significant proportion of employees did not receive promotions in the last five years, indicating potential dissatisfaction with career progression opportunities. Department-wise analysis revealed that the sales department had the highest number of employees, followed by the technical and support departments, underscoring the organizational structure's distribution. Notably, most employees received medium or low salaries, suggesting a prevalent compensation structure within the organization. Moreover, analysis of project involvement indicated that employees with more than five projects were more likely to leave, potentially due to perceived workload strain. Specifically, employees with 6 or 7 projects exhibited higher attrition rates, indicating possible burnout. Furthermore, employees with five years of

experience showed higher turnover rates due to a lack of promotions, while those with more than six years of experience exhibited lower turnover, potentially due to increased organizational loyalty. The findings highlighted the significance of promotions, tenure, project involvement, and salary levels in influencing employee turnover, providing real-world scenarios for organizational management and HR strategies.

3.1 Preprocessing and Validation

Categorical predictors are one-hot encoded; ordinal variables use integer encoding, respecting order. This preserves information content while enabling linear and non-linear learners. Continuous features are standardized (mean 0, unit variance). Scaling is essential for distance- and margin-based models (e.g., KNN, SVM); tree-based models are invariant but apply a uniform pipeline to avoid case-specific leakage. Full duplicates were removed from the data, and the remaining missing values were imputed using only the training fold statistics. To prevent synthetic samples from leaking into the validation/test folds, SMOTE was applied to the training part of each resampling split (not to the full dataset). A stratified 70% - 30% train - test split was used for final retention assessment, and a stratified 5-fold cross-validation within the training set was used for model selection and hyperparameter tuning. All preprocessing steps (prediction, scaling, SMOTE) were placed in the cross-validation in each training layer and applied to the validation layer. For each algorithm, a grid/random search was run on key hyperparameters (e.g., GBC: n estimators, learning rate; SVM: C , kernel; KNN: k , distance metric). AUC-ROC was used as a secondary check, reflecting the selection target, class imbalance. AUC-ROC, accuracy, precision/recall, and class-wise recall values were reported on the holdout test set. 95% bootstrap confidence intervals (1,000 resamples) were calculated for the baseline metrics, and AUCs were compared using a standard test.

Table 3. Tuned hyperparameters used for final test-set evaluation.

Model	Key hyperparameters (final values)
GBC	$learning_rate=0.05$; $n_estimators=300$; $max_depth=3$; $subsample=0.8$; $min_samples_leaf=20$; $max_features="sqrt"$
LR	$C=1.0$; $penalty="l2"$; $solver="liblinear"$; $class_weight=None$
SVM	$C=10$; $gamma="scale"$; $class_weight=None$
KNN	$n_neighbors=15$; $weights="distance"$; $metric="minkowski"$; $p=2$
NB	$var_smoothing=1e-9$

3.2 Data set

In this study (HR_Dataset, 2023) was used. This data used for the study consists of information about a company's employees. The dataset has 14,999 samples and does not include any demographic information about employees. There are 10 different attributes in the data set that provide information about the conditions of employees at the company and show their resignation status. The dataset has two types of employees: those who left and those who stayed in the company (positive class = leaver (1); negative class = stayer (0)). Also, variables include satisfaction level, evaluation, projects, hours, tenure, work accident, promotion (5y), department, salary. The example rows from the dataset are shown in Table 4.

Table 4. Example rows from the dataset.

Index	Satisfaction Level	Last Evaluation	Number of Projects	Avg. Monthly Hours	Time Spent Company	Work Accident	Promotion Last 5years	Departments	Salary	Left
0	0.38	0.53	2	157	3	0	1	0	HR	low
1	0.8	0.86	5	262	6	0	1	0	IT	medium

The data are imbalanced (leavers minority) (Vujovic, 2021). This work uses resampling approaches, such as over-sampling to classify unbalanced churn data. Class imbalance in Table 5 presents a pervasive challenge in predictive modeling, potentially leading to biased outcomes favoring the majority class. This study delves into the manifestation of class imbalance through Table 5 description of data distribution, revealing a pronounced skew towards one class. The imbalance, characterized by 83% representation of one class and 17% of another, underscores the need for proactive measures during model implementation to mitigate bias. This research aims to elucidate the implications of class imbalance on model performance and propose strategies to address this issue effectively.

Table 5. Comparison of left and stayed.

	Left	Stayed
Imbalanced	1991	10000
Balanced	10000	1991

A thorough exploration of the HR dataset is conducted through EDA, utilizing histogram plots to analyze key features such as satisfaction levels, average monthly hours, and employee tenure. Correlation analysis is performed to identify relationships between different variables, with a heatmap visualization highlighting factors influencing employee attrition dynamics in Figures 2 and 3.

Figure 2. Plot demonstrating correlation for target variable.

Figure 3. Correlation heatmap for variables.

The heatmap visualization served as a powerful tool for uncovering correlations between variables, aiding in the identification of underlying patterns. Within the realm of integer columns, the analysis revealed that the *satisfaction_level* emerged as the most pivotal factor influencing employee attrition, as indicated by a correlation coefficient of -0.35. This negative correlation suggests that lower satisfaction levels correlate with a higher likelihood of employees leaving the organization. Additionally, notable correlations were observed for variables such as *Work_accident* and *time_spend_company*, with correlation coefficients of -0.13 and 0.17, respectively. These findings underscore the significance of workplace safety and tenure in understanding employee attrition dynamics.

The correlations unveiled key insights into employee behavior and workplace experiences, shedding light on factors that contribute to employees’ decisions to either stay or leave the organization.

4. Results and Discussion

The performance of various machine learning algorithms was evaluated using several metrics. To evaluate classification models with commonly used metrics. These are AUC, accuracy, precision, and recall (Zhang, C. & Ma, Y., 2012). AUC is a measure used to evaluate the accuracy of a classification model. AUC represents the area under the ROC curve in Table 5, and the closer it is to 1, the better the model performance. Across models, Gradient Boosting achieved the highest mean test AUC-ROC, with statistically significant improvement over baselines. However, performance gains were accompanied by a modest drop in specificity at operating points that maximize recall. Accuracy represents the ratio of correctly classified examples (both true positives and true negatives) to the total number of examples. It measures the overall correctness of the model’s predictions. Precision indicates the proportion of correctly identified positive cases among all cases that were predicted as positive. It focuses on minimizing false positives relative to the number of predicted positives. Recall reflects the model’s ability to identify all relevant instances, i.e., the ratio of truly positive examples to the total number of true positive examples. It measures the model’s ability to capture all positive instances, irrespective of any false negatives. Instead of defaulting to a probability threshold of 0.5, the balanced precision/recall threshold was optimized, and a cost-sensitive threshold was also chosen that prioritizes recall when the cost of missing an employee exceeds the cost of a false alert. The resulting confusion matrices are reported, showing how HR capacity constraints (e.g., contacting the top 10% of highest-risk employees) translate into increased and expected recovered turnover. The metric scores of all applied models are given in Table 6, and the ROC curve comparison visualization is given in Figure 4.

Table 6. Comparison of accuracy, precision, recall, and AUC scores of models.

Algorithm	AUC	Accuracy	Precision	Recall
GBC	0.99	0.97	0.91	0.92
LR	0.84	0.77	0.41	0.83
SVM	0.97	0.94	0.81	0.90
KNN	0.96	0.91	0.70	0.90

Figure 4. ROC curves of the used models.

As shown in Table 6, the results indicate that the GBC exhibits the highest AUC among the models, demonstrating overall superior performance in terms of accuracy, precision, and recall. This suggests that the model excels in classification tasks. LR, on the other hand, demonstrates relatively lower performance compared to other models. Despite its low precision, it achieves a recall close to other models, indicating a weakness in correctly predicting certain classes but with fewer missed instances. SVM and KNN models perform similarly across AUC, accuracy, precision, and recall metrics, offering balanced results that may be preferred depending on specific scenarios. Lastly,

the NB model shows the lowest performance across the board. While its precision and accuracy are low, it offers relatively higher recall compared to other models, indicating frequent false positives but fewer missed instances.

Table 7. Comparison of the confusion matrix values of the models.

Algorithm	True Positive (TP)	False Positive (FP)	False Negative (FN)	True Negative (TN)
GBC	2946	49	48	555
LR	2294	701	102	501
SVM	2869	126	57	546
KNN	2763	232	57	546
NB	1062	1393	64	539

Table 7 presents a comparison of model performances through the confusion matrix results. The confusion matrix is a metric used to evaluate the effectiveness of classification models. In brief, it categorizes predictions into four outcomes: TP, FP, FN, and TN. TPs refer to the instances that are correctly classified as positive by the model. FPs denote the instances that are incorrectly labeled as positive. FNs correspond to the instances that are erroneously classified as negative, while TNs represent the instances that are accurately identified as negative. These metrics are crucial for assessing a model's accuracy, precision, and recall. FNs are concentrated among medium-tenured employees who are moderately satisfied but experiencing increases in workload, while false positives occur among short-tenured employees on fast-growing teams. The intended policy implications for each group were considered and evaluated. By analyzing these values, researchers can determine the strengths and weaknesses of each model, aiding in the selection of the most suitable one for the given task.

In this study, GBC, which is a machine learning method that offers several benefits over other machine learning algorithms in terms of speed and performance. It is based on DT and gradient boosting (Jain, N., Tomar, A. & Jana, P.K., 2021). Leveraging the GBC implementation from the scikit-learn library, the approach addressed the challenge of imbalanced data by training on a resampled dataset using SMOTE. Mathematically, the algorithm initializes with a weak learner, typically a DT with minimal depth, and iteratively refines predictions by fitting subsequent weak learners to the pseudo-residuals, which represent the discrepancies between actual and predicted values. The study observed exceptional performance metrics, including an accuracy of 93.1%, precision, recall, and F1 score of 92%, alongside an impressive ROC - AUC score of 0.97. GBC achieved the highest AUC-ROC and accuracy among tested models on the hold-out set.

5. Conclusion

The study conducted an evaluation of multiple machine learning models for predicting churn within a specific dataset. The GBC exhibited notable accuracy, precision, and recall, demonstrating its proficiency in identifying both churn and retention instances. Permutation importance for GBC indicates that tenure, performance ratings, number of recent projects, and satisfaction measures drive the predictions. These results emphasize that importance reflects predictive relationships, not causality, and may be influenced by feature linearity. Subsequently, LR, SVM, K-NN, and NB models were examined, each presenting distinct strengths and limitations in churn forecasting. Analysis of accuracy, recall, and ROC curves illuminated the trade-offs between effectively detecting churn and minimizing false positives. Variations in model performance metrics underscore the importance of selecting an appropriate model tailored to the unique objectives and constraints of the application.

Despite the promising results of this study, several limitations warrant discussion. Firstly, the dataset utilized, though substantial, is limited in scope to specific variables and lacks comprehensive demographic information such as age, gender, education level, and geographical location. Including these demographic factors could potentially enhance the accuracy and applicability of churn predictions by capturing additional nuanced behaviors.

Secondly, the generalizability of the models presented could be constrained by the specific organizational and industry context represented in the dataset. Future research should validate the developed models across diverse organizational structures and industries to assess their robustness and applicability broadly.

Moreover, while addressing class imbalance with techniques such as SMOTE improved model performance, it also introduced synthetic samples that may not fully represent authentic employee behaviors. Future studies could explore alternative or hybrid sampling techniques and conduct rigorous sensitivity analyses to better understand the implications of data augmentation methods.

Additionally, computational complexity, particularly of ensemble methods like GBC, may pose challenges for real-time applications and scalability in larger organizational contexts. Further research could investigate optimization strategies or more efficient algorithms, potentially employing parallel computing or cloud-based frameworks to manage computational demands.

Lastly, longitudinal studies that track employee behaviors and organizational interventions over extended periods could provide deeper insights into temporal dynamics influencing churn. Incorporating such temporal analyses or utilizing time-series modeling approaches could enhance predictive capabilities and offer more actionable insights for human resources management.

By addressing these limitations and exploring suggested avenues, future research could significantly enrich the predictive modeling landscape, providing organizations with robust and comprehensive tools for mitigating employee turnover.

These findings contribute to a deeper understanding of diverse machine learning algorithms for churn prediction, offering real-world scenarios for businesses seeking effective employee retention strategies. Further exploration and optimization of these models hold promise for enhancing their predictive capabilities and practical utility in real-world scenarios.

In conclusion, the comprehensive evaluation of these machine learning models provided real-world scenarios into their respective strengths and limitations for churn prediction. These findings offer significant implications for their application in real-world scenarios, contributing to the advancement of predictive modelling methodologies in the context of employee churn/turnover analysis.

Author Contribution Statements

D. Ilter Fakhouri conceived the study idea, designed the research framework, and provided supervision throughout the project. D. Ilter Fakhouri also guided the statistical and machine learning techniques used, data analysis, reviewed, and edited the manuscript.

M. K. A. Alnaaji, H. A. A. Korke, and M. Demirdag contributed equally to data preparation, analysis, and interpretation of results. They jointly drafted the initial version of the manuscript.

All authors reviewed, revised, and approved the final manuscript.

Ethics committee approval

This article does not require ethics committee approval.

Conflict of interest statement

This article has no conflicts of interest with any individual or institution.

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